

COMPOSING CREATIVITY IN POP AND JAZZ ART

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the characteristics of pop-jazz music art in modern composer's work.

Key words: Art, musical genre, Estrada, Jazz, musical culture, composer's creativity.

Introduction.

Musical variety is a means of actively developing emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. It is known that by getting to know music, you can enjoy music for a lifetime. In general, music is an integral part of the human psyche. Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality.

Music performance, which is considered important in the history of world music, is based on the solo performance style according to its essence, but it also requires ensemble performance. Therefore, piano lessons occupy an important place in the educational programs and plans of musical educational institutions for teaching the piano specialty¹. It is not without reason that in the piano class of children's music and art schools, the student not only completes the initial stage of musical literacy, but also acquires the skill of playing in cooperation for the first time.

In music, the Jazz genre teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste, shapes his spiritual outlook. This system has the ability to strongly influence human feelings and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral education.

By modern composer's creativity, we can understand the creation of works in various genres formed as a result of the musical development of the peoples of the whole world. For example, works in the following musical genres: opera, ballet, oratorio, cantata, symphonies, all stage musical works, choral works, instrumental works - quartets, sonatas and melodies, vocal works - romances, songs. and the creators who can create works can be called modern composers. We all know very well that the role and importance of modern composer's art in our spirituality and cultural development is great.

It is known that each era or time has its own spiritual world based on its level of development. The demand specific to the needs of the society is formed in proportion to the time of the worldviews suitable to the taste. The new way of thinking, attitudes and worldviews formed due to our independence are the basis of our unique idea of national independence. This is a sign of the spiritual perfection of the future great country. Today's

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

main demands are to be independent in every field, to restore our national values and to operate within the framework of world standards. We can see this in the rapid development of modern composers' work and in the spread of pop music forms among our people. In our music, universal musical forms, imbued with the spirit of the times, are developing more and more. It should be noted that the original state of our modern music is being enriched with new secular genres, typical of our day. Folk music can be said to be the manifestation of our national traditions and rituals in the tones. These examples are closely related to the daily life, training and national values of our people. In order to preserve them and pass them on to the next generation, special folklore ensembles have been established and are currently operating.

Pop music. The word Estrada means "hill" (supa) in Latin. In the 50s of the 20th century, the word pop entered music and began to be used as a small form of performing arts. Pop music is a leading part of pop art. Estrada is popular music of a light household character, the history of its formation begins with the theater and performance forms of Western nations. It developed from the interaction of the coffeehouse and music hall cultures popularized in the West. Slow jazz, European and Eastern harmony and rhythm, rock, pop, etc. In Uzbekistan, pop music began to form in the 50s of the 20th century². It was founded by the well-known pop star Botir Zakirov. In 1957, the young pop group from Uzbekistan successfully participated for the first time in the VI International Festival of Youth held in Moscow and won the proud 4th place. It was a great achievement. After that, pop music quickly became popular and developed. Pop groups such as "Yalla", "Pakhtaoy", "Navo", "Sado" were formed.

Estrada music occupies a special place in the work of modern composers. A number of Uzbek composers have created and continue to work in this direction. For example, Rustam Abdullayev, Khabibullo Rahimov, Nadim Narkhodjayev, Dilorom Amannulayeva, Avaz Mansurov, Khurshida Hasanova, Aydin Abdullayeva and many other young composers are working effectively. Working in the pop song genre requires a lot from the composer: to have a sensitive sense of time, to be a kind of "barometer", to take into account the artistic taste of the audience, to choose appropriate topics. Describing pop songs of Uzbek composers, it should be noted that they correspond to the general development of our time. "The stylistic direction in pop art," says D. Amanullayeva, "is a unique "fashion" determined by the era and the listener. The song is a reflection of time, a "mirror" of our life.

For the development of pop songs, the composer D. Amanullayev has published a number of academic manuals: "Pop Songs" (Tashkent., 2007), pop-jazz vocalists (Tashkent., 2014), pop songs songs (Tashkent., 2015), which are included in the educational process and are fundamental educational material for pop students. In this genre, only composers who are in tune with the times will be able to achieve their good results. The uniqueness of the pop genre, which has brought many composers of Uzbekistan wide popularity among the mass audience, has opened a new, interesting, active creative path for many composers.

In the 1970s and 1980s, almost all the composers of that time, Mutal Burkhanov, Manas Leviyev, Sharif Ramazanov, Gafur Kadirov, I. Akbarov, I. Hamrayev, worked in the genre of pop music, and this is connected with the search for unique means of national expression. was

² Amanullaeva D. Review of stylistic directions of vocal and jazz art of Uzbekistan (1991 – 2009) // Processes of reforming the system of music education. T., 2009.

liq. Composer Ikram Akbarov's pop songs such as "Ra'no", "Gazli kokhliklari", "Azizim", "Lolazor chorlaydi", which were specially written and performed for the first time by the famous Estrada singer, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Botir Zakirov, are among the works of the Uzbek Estrada composer gained fame with his charm. This rise in pop art gave the world bright examples, which later became classics of Uzbek pop art. Also, as we know, children's songs occupy a special place in pop music, they require the composer to know children's psychology, children's vocal data and vocal abilities, the ability to sensitively feel the children's world, its variety and diversity. One of the signs of the renewal of the musical system of the composer's children's song is the extensive use of pop music techniques expected from the previous experiences of the composers and the activities of the first children's VIA, created in the 1980s.

The pop song by the Uzbek composer focuses on people, their feelings and thoughts. In this genre, various topics and plots aimed at reflecting modern human life and its time are covered³. Composers find their own rhythm intonations, means of musical expression, placement of musical materials for their songs, but the most important thing in songs is the melody that composers create from the best musical language - chanting, characteristic of Uzbek song lyrics, and thus continuing the tradition. Today, Uzbek pop music corresponds to the basics of musical art trends and meets all the requirements and indicators of this genre.

Conclusion.

As a conclusion, we can say that one of the characteristic aspects of pop-jazz music of the current era is that composers are "discovering" different stages of jazz, and the ideological-symbolic directions are becoming more complex. In this regard, there is a need to analyze jazz works in order to observe such complex processes of composers. They are characterized by a variety of cadences: complex fourth-fifth structures in the range of seconds, melodic lines rich in chromatic tones, polyfunctional structures that occur during the melodic movement, etc.

³ History of Uzbek Soviet music, volume III. T., 1991.

References:

- 1.Amanullayeva D. Review of stylistic directions of vocal and jazz art of Uzbekistan (1991 – 2009) // Processes of reforming the system of music education. T., 2009.
- 2.Bulatnov S. Earl Hines [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://bulswing.ru/?p=781> (entry date: 17.02.2020).
- 3.“Jazz Origins in New Orleans – New Orleans Jazz National Historical Park”. National Park Service.
- 4.Great people of jazz ed. K. Moshkova. Sankt-Peterburg: Doe; PLANET MUSIC, 2009. 736 b.
- 5.Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
- 6.Kurakin I. Herbi Xankok “Globalizes jazz” // Culture. 2009 y. 32-s.